

“Cold Headed” Research and Emotional Design, A Social Approach

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Abstract

Designers are often asked to devise solutions to problems or situations relating to the diverse aspects of human activities. It is mostly regarded as utilitarian approach where fusion of ideas and action tools from diverse sources is employed to arrive at the optimal functional solution.

In the present work, a specific step in the qualification of design arts teachers is evaluated. This step, comprising the experience of a course, begins with studies of research methods, goes through action research and concludes with socially motivated design projects for special needs and environments. Socially motivated designing becomes a result of a growing emotional involvement of the students with the diverse groups of people with whom they come in contact during the research process.

During the course the students are simultaneously exposed to texts emerging from two different disciplines and they perform under their combined influence. One discipline is scientific-engineering and the other is the social-ethical domain. The students are instructed to perform “cold headed” research in fields such as: environments, sociology, pedagogy and psychology, engineering and even medicine.

The topics of the course are leading the students to accumulate theoretical knowledge combined with the creation of ideas and propositions for actual objects and environments. The last are presented as sheer hypothesis, research questions, and are therefore proposals awaiting further research and possible future implementation.

Focusing on groups with special needs in domains such as: education, learning environments, quality of life and influencing environments, promotes social involvements and emotional sensibility. This sensibility is reflected both in their human interactions as well as in their design proposals.

Keywords: design education, research methods, hypothesis, design for needs, social approach

Introduction

Some approach which review design activity regard it, on a whole, as having an educational nature. It is a well-known fact that product in general and designed one in particular, have a certain impact on viewers and users [1]. In addition, it can be assumed that many designers aim that their product(s) should have a certain impact on the user. These interrelations between designers and users are negotiated through product(s) issued by designers. The evaluation of the nature of these interrelations is extremely intricate, as it calls not only for

the implementation of disciplinary, independent reference parameters, but also interdisciplinary considerations of complicated nature [2].

Over the years, comprehensive suggestions focusing on the role design should play in consumers, utilitarian societies have been introduced (Fuller 1970), (Papanek 1972), (Papanek 1988). In general, these suggestions view design as an activity that should reflect holistic attitude where everyday practices are derived also from moral consideration [3]. Moreover, these approaches categorically emphasize what is “right” in practicing design while designers and their “state of mind”, are barely or briefly considered.

The approach in short mentioned above, regarding design as educational activity and in return, designers as educators, although limited in scope and elaboration is coherently embedded in the Design Arts Department at Teacher’s College of Technology.

Teaching at its prime, apart from the obvious disciplinary skills, demands a certain social and emotional awareness and involvement. The same applies when it comes to the teaching of would be teachers [4] in the various disciplines of design. During the period of their qualification, students have to acquire a large volume of knowledge and skills.

Learning in a demanding and relatively dense academic program leaves very little space for emotional involvement. In spite of that, the present report indicates that by taking simple steps and inducing the proper attitude, it is possible to create a learning environment where students are emotionally involved.

Description

Over the last five years, students of the third year, from the Design Arts Department at Teacher’s College of Technology in Tel-Aviv, Israel, participated in a non-elective course of 2 semesters [5].

In the course, “*Research Methods and Designing Influencing Environments and Objects*”, the first 7 weeks are dedicated to theoretical aspects of research and research methods. Topics such as: scientific approach [6], pure and applied research, “exact” science(s) versus “liberal-

arts or social” science(s), hypothesis formulation, induction and deduction and other relevant subjects are reviewed and discussed.

In parallel to the somewhat emotionally removed dealing with research methods, the students are asked [7] to screen human activities of groups or individuals with special needs. As “special needs” has a wide range of connotations, in this case it implies the needs of people, to mention just a few, experiencing: various disabilities, attention and learning disorder, prematurely born babies, muscular damage.

The students then form working teams, 2 to 5 students in a team, assigned to explore in detail the many aspect of life of people with special needs. This stage of field-research lasts for about 5 weeks and includes literature review, visits to various relevant sites including hospitals and hostels, interviewing staff-members and individuals, compilation of questionnaire and data processing.

In the final 2 weeks of the first semester, each team is occupied with the formulation of a design proposal relating and meeting the ends of a specific need. As it is course in research methods, the proposals have the nature of hypothesis and are composed as “if...then...”

At this stage it is clear that the designed future final product [8], expected to be produced under relevant designing consideration, will merely stand as a proposal, hypothesis, staying open for further evaluation.

The second semester is dedicated to the design and production of the desired product. At this phase, work continues in the following conditions:

1. On a weekly basis, 2 instructors work with each team of students. The first one is a veteran designer, while the second is engineer having needed knowledge in research methods and a sound understanding in designing practices [9].
2. Ideas and proposals forwarded by students are discussed and scrutinized in accordance with various parameters that include, to mention just the cardinal: logic of operation and function, human factors and size, materials, shape and design language.
3. Simultaneously, students go on with their dialogue with the potential users on a continuous basis, seeking for suitable alternations and adaptations in their product.

Observations and discussion

One of the first and most significant result [10] is achieved and observed at the end of the first semester, after students come with contact with or are exposed to the special needs of certain groups and/or individuals.

For students, most of them can be regarded as “young and healthy” individuals the encounter with human disabilities, special needs and suffering is not a straightforward experience [11]. In the context of the College situation and footnote [11], the tendency is to continue and maintain daily routines “normal” as possible. At times it not easy as life shattering events occur at close distances. In any case, students do not sink in “self-pity” although most of them are troubled by the geopolitical situation in the region.

As a result of this experience, the students, in a relatively short period of time, show certain maturity and tend to be more reflective towards their activities. Simultaneously, a sharp transition from “cold headed” research to emotional involvement towards the “subject” grows markedly stronger and is therefore observed. To illustrate the transition from “cold-headed” research to emotional involvement one has just to consider 2 frequent phrases expressed by students: “it is not an easy life for these people...”, “we have to do something for them...”. It appears that the students “oscillate” relatively smoothly between “cold-headed” and emotional involvement. Moreover, their awareness for issues addressing social agenda such as education, welfare, public health is sharpened even more. In addition to that, as involvement and sensibility develops [12], their self-confidence and self-awareness grow as well [13]. This growth is not associated with arrogance; on the contrary, most of the students exhibit a more accommodating and restrained behavior.

Although this report deals with the transformation students undergo during an annual course, the attached 3 Figures serve only as an example of a “material” result to what is mostly an emotional process. Apart from the 3 examples, in the last 5 years the students introduced over 25 designed propositions including, mentioning just a few:

1. Communication console for a child staying for long periods of time in hospital. The system enables child to keep on line contact with his teachers and friends at school.

2. Modified table for children having ADHD/“hyperactive”, permitting their integration in a regular classroom.
3. Modified computer keyboard for children having ADHD/“hyperactive”, permitting their integration in a regular classroom.
4. Assembly games for individuals with vision disability.
5. Modified horse saddle for zotherapy.
6. Semi-transparent, acoustically isolated transportable module placed in public libraries enabling group learning without disturbing the other users of the library.

Figure 1, The production of a modified handle of a wheel chair designed to contain a swivel lever for an easy-touch, “pop-up” mobile telephone. Students are taking measures for final adjustments, **a.** Prototype of a telephone holder, **b.**

Figure 2, A balanced buoy for Hydrotherapy designed to support children undergoing treatment in a swimming pool. A child using the buoy in a swimming pool-an illustration, **a**.
A real buoy, **b**.

Figure 3, An assembly game designed to improve mechanical skills of children. The black patches serve as attachment links between the assembly parts. (two different views of the game).

Conclusions

1. Through elaborate and open discussions it is possible to induce a voluntary emotional attitude from design students.
2. Emotional involvement serves as strong driving force in accelerating the readiness of students to deal with what might be considered as not-easy issues in human experience.
3. Students encountering “cold headed” research interlocked with emotional engagement tend to develop self-awareness and sensibility towards social issues.

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NOTES

[1] Although there are individuals able physically use a variety of products without actually employing viewing senses. It is also true all the way around. Therefore, for convenience and brevity, we will designate individuals interacting with product(s), one way or the other, as users.

[2] Disciplinary parameters may include “shape”, “line”, “balance” etc.; Interdisciplinary considerations, to mention just a few, are “culture”, “aesthetics” and “psychology”.

[3] In our opinion, environmental considerations in design emerge basically from moral attitudes, although they are forwarded via practical and utilitarian argumentation.

[4] Would be teachers in the present study are students.

[5] Two academic semesters is normally in Israel 30 weeks. In the present particular case, each week included 4 hours meeting.

[6] Based mostly on what is known as western culture scientific dogma and practice. It is an arbitrary choice not indicating any superiority over possible dogma of other cultures.

[7] It is a delicate phase, as personal preferences of students stand on one hand, the social and emotional call to response to possible needs, stands on the other. This phase is therefore negotiated with the help of intensive discussions emphasizing the special role designer plays in the intricate fabric of human activities.

[8] The final product is completed and introduced at the end of the second semester.

[9] This cooperation, basically multidisciplinary and performed simultaneously, in real time with students, requires reduction of barriers, mostly imaginary, that prone to “pop-up” whenever people from different disciplines have to work together.

[10] As this report is based on experience and not on a carefully controlled experiment, we prefer to use “observations” rather “results”, although we use the word “results” but in a broader and less constrictive connotation.

[11] Israel is located in a conflict afflicted zone and reports, visual and/or verbal, of armed activities resulting in fatalities and injuries are almost a daily routine. The impression of the authors is that although individuals tend to develop a distinct division between experiences related to “political” events and experiences having a more personal/private nature, the inclination of projects proposed by the students has a universal scope.

[12] It is reflected in the extra many hours that the students are ready to allocate for the project; the empathy they show for disabled individuals whom they meet during the course; the rhetoric they use, passionate at times, in describing their progress.

[13] Although growing relatively slowly, these qualities show themselves especially when students have to evaluate their own achievements or when they build and forward various, critical at times, argumentation. Few, for example, do not hesitate and are confident enough to propose alternative academic agenda.

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